

DUAL-643 GHZ AND 874 GHZ AIRBORNE RADIOMETERS FOR ICE CLOUD MEASUREMENTS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ice clouds are a key atmospheric entity that couple the global hydrologic and energy cycles and modulate the climate system response to changes in global forcing. Most ice cloud measurements conducted in the past by aircraft or satellite sensors have been limited to the visible and infrared regions of the spectrum. Retrievals of cloud parameters from these sensors are generally limited to regions near the top of the ice clouds. To probe denser ice clouds and study their microphysical properties requires sensors at longer wavelengths.

Theoretical analyses have shown that millimeter and sub-millimeter wave radiometric measurements can provide an improved characterization of ice clouds that contributes significantly to our understanding of the global water cycle and thus climate predictability [1], [2]. Studies have shown that the two highest absorption windows with acceptable transmission in millimeter wave and sub-millimeter wave range are around 643 GHz and 874 GHz. To utilize this potential, dual polarization 643 GHz and single polarization 874 GHz receivers were recently developed for airborne CoSSIR, Compact Scanning Sub-millimeter wave Imaging Radiometer.

2. AIRBORNE COSSIR

The primary version of CoSSIR was composed of six total power millimeter and sub-millimeter wave radiometers at the frequencies of 183, 220, 380, 487 (V & H), and 640 GHz. The 487 GHz channel was dual (V & H) polarized and the remaining channels were single polarized. The instrument was first flown on board the NASA

ER-2 aircraft during CRYSTAL-FACE in July 2002. After some improvement, the instrument was flown again on board the NASA WB-57 aircraft during the first phase of the CR-AVE in January 2006.

Studies have shown that water vapor absorption reduces sensitivity to lower clouds for frequencies above 500 GHz. Lower millimeter wave range have less water vapor absorption and can thus sense lower altitude ice clouds, which tend to have large particles. Simulations demonstrate that the higher frequencies, particularly at 874 GHz, are highly sensitivity to scattering by ice particles. Simulating the polarization ratios of 640 GHz brightness temperature demonstrates greater sensitivity to particle size.

Consequently, multiple sub-millimeter wave frequency, 183 GHz ~ 874 GHz, measurements on water vapor lines provide humidity profile and cloud height information, thereby providing a unique measurement of ice clouds. In order to extend the frequency range of CoSSIR from 643 GHz to 874 GHz, a dual polarization 643 GHz and a single polarization 874 GHz receivers were recently developed. The design and development of these receivers will be described in the next two sections.

The latest version of CoSSIR that measured radiation at the frequencies of 183, 220, 380, 643 (V & H) and 874 GHz was flown for the TC4 field campaign in July ~ August, 2007.

3. DESIGN OF RECEIVERS

The dual 643 GHz receivers are driven by two independent Gunn oscillators with operating frequencies at 80.375 GHz. Each source signal is fed into a cascade of two varactor doublers and its frequency is multiplied up to 321.5 GHz with a

4mW power level to provide a LO power for 643 GHz sub-harmonic mixer.

Due to considerations of frequency stability for the 874 GHz receiver, a DRO (Dielectric Resonator Oscillator) output frequency of 36.417 GHz is selected for the driving source of the 874 GHz receiver. After the source power is amplified by an RF amplifier, the signal frequency is multiplied by 12 with a cascaded chain composed of a frequency quadrupler and tripler. Consequently, a signal at frequency of 437 GHz with a 2.5 mW power level is produced to be used for a LO power of 874 GHz sub-harmonic mixer.

The frequency stability of the LO was degraded with the multiplication of the fundamental frequency. For the dual 643 GHz receivers, the frequency stability of Gunn oscillators was typically at 8 MHz/ $^{\circ}$ C. But the stability of the LO was reduced to 32 MHz/ $^{\circ}$ C. In order to keep the down converted IF signal within the IF band a frequency band of 0.1 ~ 6.0 GHz was chosen.

The DRO chosen was of high quality with frequency stability of 3.5 MHz/ $^{\circ}$ C for the 874 GHz LO chain. Since the fundamental frequency was multiplied by 12 and there were other frequency stability issues in the 874 GHz channel, an IF bandwidth of 0.5 ~ 8.0 GHz was selected.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF RADIOMETERS

In the CoSSIR radiometer, stages of multipliers were employed to multiply frequencies up to the LO frequencies. The forwards biases of the multipliers induced by the input RF powers were sensitive to the input power levels and physical temperatures. During the development, heat sinking was properly mounted on the multipliers to keep temperatures at a certain range; thermal control chips were attached on the Gunn oscillators to control operating temperatures; and layouts were carefully considered to avoid interference among the channels.

Some innovations were implemented during the development of the 874 GHz receiver. In the primary version, a DRO was operating at a frequency of 12.140 GHz. A tripler and RF amplifier output frequency of 36.420 GHz was connected to the next stage with a WR-22 flange. In the latest version, a DRO frequency of 36.417

GHz was selected and a K-connector to replace the WR-22 flange in the tripler and amplifier. These approaches significantly reduced DC power supply and volume allowing the entire receivers to be integrated into the original drum

5. THE CoSSIR DRUM

The CoSSIR drum, a cylinder 8.5" diameter and 11" length (bronze colored object underneath), with the control unit is shown in Figure 1

Fig. 1 The CoSSIR drum with the control unit.

The calibration references of the drum were composed of two close coupled external black bodies at the temperatures of ~250K and ~300K. The external blackbody measured to an accuracy of +/- 0.1K provided a calibration accuracy of +/- 0.7K in the brightness temperature range of 200 ~ 300K.

The scan geometry of CoSSIR was software programmable with versatile scan modes. It can be programmed to perform a conical scan with incidence angles between 0° ~ 54° , or an across track scan, or a combination of both. The details of the scan pattern can be found in Wang et al. [3].

6 LABORATORY CALIBRATION

A few series of laboratory calibration tests of the instrument were conducted with a liquid nitrogen (LN₂) calibration load to verify and enhance radiometry performance. An across track scan mode was programmed in these tests, with

the antenna beams pointing at three fixed scenes of cold, hot, and LN₂ loads, after the initial instrument warm up of about 30 minutes. A blower was used to apply cold air at the drum continually to keep the Gunn oscillators from overheating.

Calibration data was used to adjust bias voltages and video-amps gains to balance the performance of the 643 GHz dual channels. After several testing cycles, the measured brightness temperature differences of the 643 GHz dual channels were within 1.0 K during laboratory calibrations.

House keeping data was used to improve the performance of the 874 GHz receiver. The test data showed that the temperature variations of the DRO were less than expected. But the temperature changes of the RF amplifier were still uncontrollable, which seriously affected the LO power level and performance sensitivity.

The laboratory calibrations provided unique information about how to adjust bias voltages on each stage and balance the entire operations. The adjustments enhanced performance of receivers, resulting in a system noise temperature, T_{sys} , of 4000 K for the 643 GHz receiver and 8000 K for the 874 GHz receiver.

7. TC4 FIELD CAMPAIGN

The TC4 field campaign was conducted in Costa Rica during July 15 thru August 10, 2007. CoSSIR was on board the NASA ER-2 aircraft, which normally flew with a cruising altitude of about 20 km. The measurements were therefore above all clouds systems.

A segment of brightness temperature map and variations along the flight path acquired by CoSSIR are shown in Figure 2 and 3. Brightness temperature map and variations were obtained at an observation angle of 53.6° in the forward direction during a flight on July 17, 2007 over ocean areas south of San Jose, Costa Rica.

The brightness temperature map shows that the regions of low brightness temperatures are a result of millimeter wave and sub-millimeter wave scattering by ice particles in the clouds. The scattering is strongly frequency dependent, the higher the frequency the stronger the scattering. The dispersion in the scattering signatures near the

water vapor line of 183 and 380 GHz are caused by water vapor absorption.

Fig. 2. A segment of BT map acquired by CoSSIR

Fig. 3. BT variations along the flight path

For light to moderate ice clouds, the high-frequency channels, particularly at 874 GHz, in panel 3 of Figure 3 clearly show a much higher sensitivity to scattering by ice particles. In the cloud free regions, the ratios of 640GHz brightness temperatures at V & H polarizations, displayed in the bottom panel of Figure 3, are close to unity as expected; while in the regions of ice clouds these ratios are generally below 1, clearly indicating non-spherical features of the ice particles.

8. SCIENTIFIC SIGNIFICANCE

The brightness temperature map presented above clearly demonstrates the recent advance in sub-millimeter wave radiometry for ice cloud sensing. The 874 GHz radiometer greatly improves the CoSSIR sensitivity to small ice particles. This implies that CoSSIR is able to pick up the measurements of ice clouds where the visible and inferred approaches left behind, i.e. saturated. The polarization measurement capability at 643 GHz can provide information on particle shapes, as well as improve the accuracy of the ice cloud parameters retrievals, e.g., ice water path and particle size.

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10. REFERENCES

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